
**A CRITIQUE OF PRESIDENT MUHAMMADU BUHARI'S
OCTOBER 22, 2020 #ENDSARS ADDRESS AND ITS CONFORMITY
TO RHETORIC CANONS AND PROOFS OF COMMUNICATION**

DANIEL IME ETOKIDEM

Department of Mass Communication, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic

Ikot Osurua, Akwa Ibom State

Email: danetokidem@gmail.com

+2348064344222, +2348180561692

Abstract

Speeches by presidents are powerful as they not only carry the weight of policy statement or direction but possess the ability to inspire, uplift, motivate, unite, show empathy, be sensitive to the mood of the moment, or incite, arouse, mobilize, rally and galvanize a people towards an intended outcome. Whoever is giving the speech should oversee not just its creation but also its execution, because the speaker's method of delivery can have just as much effect on the audience's reception as the rhetoric it contains. This paper takes a critique at President Muhammadu Buhari's October 22, 2020 #EndSARS speech in the wake of the nationwide protest by Nigerian youths over police brutality and reforms and juxtapose it with the five Rhetorical canons; - inventio, dispositio, elucutio, memoria and delivery as well as the Rhetorical proofs; Ethos, Pathos and Logos as theorized by Aristotle and recommend that Presidential speech writers should consider the importance of adopting the rhetoric canons in future speech writing to aid delivery of speeches that will inspire, arouse and appeal to emotions while efforts should be intensified to ensure the use of the rhetorical skills in future speeches delivery to reduce over dependence on the script or teleprompter to achieve maximum rhetorical effect.

keywords: Critique, #Ends Address, Rhetoric Canons, Rhetoric Proofs, Communication

1 Introduction

Ideally, presidential speeches the world over are meant to inspire, uplift, motivate, unite, show empathy, be sensitive to the mood of the moment and presidential in nature.

Speech delivery is important. Whoever is giving the speech should oversee not just its creation but also its execution, because the speaker's method of delivery can have just as much effect on the audience's reception as the rhetoric it contains.

The writing and execution of political speeches require numerous elements of political communication. Although there is much debate about which parts of this process are the most essential, there is no doubt that its organization should place as much emphasis as possible on every detail, including composition and delivery.

Noermanzah (2018), quoting O'Sullivant *et al.* (in Alo) describe rhetoric as the practice in the use of the language of influencing others to achieve planned goals characterized by certain credibility (ethos), the ability to manage listener emotions (pathos), and the use of logic (logos). Similarly, Larson (in Altikriti) describes rhetoric as the intelligent ability to use the means of language in the process of persuasion, which can be done using ethics (ethos), emotional appeal (pathos), or reason (logos). Winkler and McCuen assert that rhetoric is a technique used by speakers or writers as an attempt to communicate with listeners or readers. He further explained that rhetoric is more the art of using linguistics or linguistic tools effectively through the choice of appropriate and effective words and the ability to manage the grammatical arrangement of sentences so as to deliver a message to the listener or writer as the speaker or author wishes. In this case, rhetoric can be interpreted as ability in the process of language tailored to the expectations of the listener or reader. Processing language, in this case, is explained by Rinaldi as the ability to effectively select and use language in certain situations with a specific purpose.

2 President Muhammadu Buhari's #Endsars Address and its Conformity to the Rhetoric Canons of Communication: An Overview

According to Esuh (2006) Classical traditions (based on Aristotle's *ad herennium*), all rhetoric is divided into five (5) parts- *inventio*, *dispositio*, *elucutio*, *memoria* and *delivery*. Each of these parts have its distinctive functions in rhetorical communication. They form part of oratorical order as well as forms for critical analysis and evaluation.

Pudewa (2016), states that Rhetoric to most modern minds, the word smacks of cunning—the empty polemic or self-aggrandizement of a political figure, or perhaps the crafty prose of a present-day sophist selling overpriced or unnecessary products to the unlearned. To those who have delved a bit into classical education, rhetoric is the third liberal art, the top of the trivium, the noble art of persuasion, a skill in the tradition of Plato and Paul, Cicero and Augustine, which since ancient times has been practiced and applied for noble (as well as ignoble) purposes.

While Walton, (2000) defines the five canons of rhetoric as invention, arrangement, style, memory and delivery.

The five canons of rhetoric are a classical approach to understanding effective communication. Invention (what to say), arrangement (structure of content), style (language choices), memory (learn the presentation) and delivery (use of more than just words).

The five canons of rhetoric are simply the five skills that individuals need to have to be great at communicating. While these canons date from a long time ago, they're still relevant for anyone looking to create and deliver effective communications today.

Explaining further, Pudewa (2016) notes that, "The word "canon" is most commonly used in music to describe a piece in which a melody is introduced in different parts successively, or in an expression like "the canon of literature": a collection of books which comprise a set such as Scripture or the Great Books. A simpler definition is "a general rule, law, or principle." The Five Canons of Rhetoric give us five general principles, or divisions, which, when we come to understand and apply them, will make our communication more effective. These principles are commonly labeled: Invention, Arrangement, Elocution, Memory, and Delivery".

On their part, Brett and McKay (2020), stated that "the Five Canons of Rhetoric constitute a system and guide on crafting powerful speeches and writing. It's also a template by which to judge effective rhetoric. The Five Canons were brought together and organized by the Roman orator Cicero, in his treatise, *De Inventione*, written around 50 BC. 150 years later in 95 AD, the Roman rhetorician Quintilian explored the Five Canons in more depth in his landmark 12-volume textbook on rhetoric, *Institutio Oratoria*. His textbook, and consequently the Five Canons of Rhetoric, went on to become the backbone of rhetorical education well into the medieval period".

They defined the five Canons of Rhetoric as:

- i. **inventio (invention):** The process of developing and refining your arguments.
- ii. **dispositio (arrangement):** The process of arranging and organizing your arguments for maximum impact.
- iii. **elocutio (style):** The process of determining how you present your arguments using figures of speech and other rhetorical techniques.
- iv. **memoria (memory):** The process of learning and memorizing your

speech so you can deliver it without the use of notes. Memory-work not only consisted of memorizing the words of a specific speech, but also storing up famous quotes, literary references, and other facts that could be used in impromptu speeches.

- v. **actio (delivery):** The process of practicing how you deliver your speech using gestures, pronunciation, and tone of voice.

2.1 President Buhari's #EndSARS address and the rhetoric Canon of Inventio (Invention)

Esuh (2006) notes that "Inventio (invention) involves the attempt on the speaker to investigate the subject matter of discourse. It embraces survey and forecasting of the subject and arguments suitable for any given rhetorical effort. It involves the idea of the status and modes of persuasion- logical, emotional and ethical, which are in themselves interrelated".

Invention is the process of coming up with what you want to say to persuade your audience of your view. What are the key messages and points that will help you convince your audience of your point of view?

To do this stage well requires clarity of purpose and understanding of the subject and your audience. At this stage you also need to choose your presentation style (and now days your medium) and decide how long your presentation should be.

To Walton, (2000), invention is the process of coming up with material for a text. In writing, this is the brainstorming or prewriting stage.

On their part, Brett and McKay (2020), stated that Invention, according to Aristotle, involves "discovering the best available means of persuasion." It may sound simple, but invention is possibly the most difficult phase in crafting a speech or piece of writing as it lays the groundwork for all the other phases; you must start from nothing to build the framework of your piece. During the Invention Phase, the goal is to brainstorm ideas on what you're going to say and how you're going to say it in order to maximize persuasion. Any good orator or writer will tell you they probably spend more time in the Invention step than they do any of the others.

Pudewa (2016) describes invention as the process of coming up with what to say. Its root is the Latin word *invenio*, meaning "to find or discover." In order to write something, we must have something to write about.

However, in the ancient rhetoric exercises known as the progymnasmata, the first task was not to “think of something to say” but to “retell a fable.” Imitation is vital to the learning of a skill.

The relationship between the words shows a truth of creativity-to invent something, you have to have some stuff to begin with. Only God produces something from nothing; the rest of us are kind of stuck with what we’ve got.

One sad fact we all must face is that we can’t get something out of a mind that isn’t in there to begin with. We can’t use words we don’t know. We can’t articulate concepts we don’t understand. We can’t think a thought we’re incapable of thinking. Which is why Memory is the foundation of all.

The President's speech under review failed this first task. He started the speech with a combative mood and spiced it with a threat. His paragraphs 1 and 2 read and sounded thus;

"It has become necessary for me to address you having heard from many concerned Nigerians and having concluded a meeting with all the Security Chiefs.

2. I must warn those who have hijacked and misdirected the initial, genuine and well-intended protest of some of our youths in parts of the country, against the excesses of some members of the now disbanded Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS).

Beginning of the second paragraph with a commanding tone, "by warning" ... "Those who have hijacked and misdirected" the protest... was saying the right thing at the wrong time. The nation was boiling, the youths were enraged, lives were lost in Lagos and across many states, words of healing, and advocacy for calm and apologizing for the failure of government to institute police reforms and create jobs for the youths would have been a better way to start.

Because to President's speech fell short of being Presidential, it failed to heal, unite, show empathy, let alone reconcile which is why it was greeted with outrage all over the country. Many saw it as empty, a waste of time and insensitive.

At the invention phase in rhetorical communication, without some direction and guidance, brainstorming can often be fruitless and frustrating. Pondering on elements such as your audience, your evidence, the means of persuasion, timing and format of argument are important and these were lacking in the

President's speech under review and using them can increase the effectiveness of your Invention sessions.

2.2 President Buhari's #EndSARS address and the rhetoric Canon of dispositio (disposition/arrangement)

According to Esuh (2006), dispositio (disposition) covers the philosophy of arrangement and orderly presentation/planning of the idea to be discussed. It assesses the selection of the subject matter into structure, determining or emphasizing how each part contributes to the unity and purpose of the speech. Classically, a speech should have the proem, the narratio and the epilogue, roughly equivalent to introduction, body and conclusion".

Walton defines arrangement as the process of deciding how to order the material in a text. In writing, this is still part of the prewriting stage. Speeches, like music, should be carefully arranged. Arrangement is the process of structuring your content. You need to put all the great things you thought of in the invention stage into a good order so that they work together and so that they help you land your message and persuade your audience.

Paragraphs 8 and 9 ought to have come much earlier in the speech where the President said;

8. "The result of this is clear to all observers: human lives have been lost; acts of sexual violence have been reported; two major correctional facilities were attacked and convicts freed; public and private properties completely destroyed or vandalized; the sanctity of the Palace of a Peace Maker, the Oba of Lagos has been violated. So-called protesters have invaded an International Airport and in the process disrupted the travel plans of fellow Nigerians and our visitors".

9. "All these executed in the name of the ENDSARS protests. I am indeed deeply pained that innocent lives have been lost. These tragedies are uncalled for and unnecessary. Certainly, there is no way whatsoever to connect these bad acts to legitimate expression of grievance of the youth of our country".

But again, the import of the message he wanted to convey, was that he missed the opportunity to emotionally connect with the pains of families who lost their loved ones and were passing through as nowhere in the paragraphs above or in their entire speech did he commiserate directly or indirectly with families that were grieving. If the President claimed he is deeply pained by the fact that

innocent lives were lost, he never showed it in his speech. He missed an opportunity to show empathy and rise to the moment as ‘Father of the nation’.

Soha (2010) captures the situation thus, "Because modern presidents display commitment and concern to a policy or issue through their public speeches—even if they are not typically successful leading public opinion—they lead by speaking about policy issues. Any variation in the level of attention through speeches, therefore, indicates that presidents are altering their leadership or governing strategies to affect their political fortunes and assist in their goal achievement.

Modern arrangement of speeches usually has three stages: introduction, body and conclusion. The classical arrangement that Cicero would have used though had five stages: *introduction, state neutral facts, make your case, refute alternative positions, and conclude your presentation*. This arrangement can still be used if you wish, though most people go with the three stage approach. It’s important to think about arrangement across all forms and mediums of communication and ensure that what is chosen is right for the audience and the chosen medium.

To Brett and McKay (2020), arrangement is simply the organization of a speech or text to ensure maximum persuasion. Classical rhetoricians divided a speech into six different parts. They are: Introduction (exordium), Statement of Facts (narratio), Division (partitio), Proof (confirmatio), Refutation (refutatio), Conclusion (peroratio)

2.3 President Buhari's #EndSARS address and the rhetoric Canon of Elocutio (Elocution/style)

Soha (2010) states that, "Presidents themselves believe that ineffective communication contributes to a failure of governance. Both Presidents Clinton and Reagan, for instance, lamented that their inability to lead the public was failure to communicate policy initiatives clearly. As others have argued, moreover, it is through devoting commitment and concern to a policy that demonstrates presidential leadership".

Esuh (2006) defines "Elocutio (Elocution) simply as, "styles or the concept of expression in language, resulting from the choice of words or the arrangement of the composition. Style is usually classified as plain, moderate, elated or grand".

Walton on his part defines style as the process of coming up with the actual words that will be used in a text. In writing, this Canon is first approached in the drafting stage and continues in the rewriting stage.

To Pudewa (2016), elocution basically means the way something is said. The vocabulary, sentence structure, and expressions used will affect the reader's perception of the ideas. Again, Memory is critical because the power of expressive language will be a function of the great database of language in the brain.

Style is the process of choosing language and constructing your presentation so as to create an emotional response. Eloquence and structuring and help achieve this outcome, as can the skilled use of emotive language and rhetorical devices such as analogy, allusion and alliteration.

To Brett and McKay (2020), when people write memos or give persuasive speeches, the focus is usually on what they're going to write or say. While it's important that you have something substantive to say, it's also important how you present your ideas. The canon of style will help you present your ideas and arguments so people will want to listen to you.

Coming back to President Buhari's speech under review, he lost the Rhetoric Canon of style when paragraphs 12, 13, 14 amounted to self praise in a manner that made no emotional appeal to the angry youths, majority of whom remain jobless. No protesting youth wanted to hear about his plans to "lift 100 million Nigerians out of poverty in the next 10 years; the creation of N75 billion National Youth Investment Fund to provide opportunities for the youths and the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Survival Fund", etc. Buhari's mention of Farmermoni, Tradermoni, Marketmoni, N-Power, N-Tech and N-Agro" as massive youth empowerment schemes his government has put in place for the youths because they were perceived as insulting and mere tokens compared to what the youths expected from their country and President.

He worsened the situation by using paragraph 14 for self praise and glorification when he stated that "No Nigerian Government in the past has methodically and seriously approached poverty-alleviation like we have done".

2.4 President Buhari's #EndSARS address and the rhetoric Canon of Memoria (Memory)

According to Esuh (2006), "Memoria (Memory) refers to the speaker's mastery

of key elements of not all of his material in sequential order associated with memorization".

Walton, (2000) defines memory as the process of committing a text to memory. Although this Canon is not as applicable to writing as it is to oratory, there are still occasions when writers must memorize their texts in order to make the delivery more effective.

On his part, Pudewa (2016) states that memory, of course, is where it all begins and ends. If, as was most often done in ancient times, one's rhetoric was spoken rather than written, it was critical that such speeches be well memorized and practiced for a powerful delivery. However, the function of memory as a component of rhetoric goes far beyond just memorizing a speech. The modern educationists who condemn memorization as useless, boring, rote, tedious, and harmful to children, fail to notice that if we hadn't memorized anything, we wouldn't know anything...The ancients called memory "the furnishing of the mind."

Memory relates to remembering enough so that you can present fully and fluently, without notes. This was essential in the Roman era when the canons were written and orators needed to speak for hours at a time. While it's perhaps slightly less important now, it's still a very useful skill.

Many great speakers visualize their presentations in advance, do "dress rehearsals", explore their environments and understand multiple layers of their presentations (from full text to a few key bullet points).

The rhetorical Canon of memory was the worst victim in this speech. Agreed President Buhari has never been a good orator but nowhere from start to finish of his address did he showed mastery of any key element of his speech. All through, he was glued to his script. Memorization became a victim of his inadequate rhetorical skill.

2.5 President Buhari's #EndSARS address and the rhetoric Canon of Delivery

Delivery, according to Esuh (2006) involves the skill of maximizing the vocal elements in relation to the bodily actions to achieve effective delivery.

Walton, (2000) defines delivery as the process of presenting a text to an audience. Like memory, delivery is less prominent in writing than in oratory;

however, there are many occasions when writers must think of how best to deliver their texts.

Delivery is the last of the five canons of rhetoric. It involves using all the tools available to you to effectively communicate. Emphasis, tone of voice, change of pace, pauses, volume, gesticulation, body language, positioning and props are all tools to help effectively deliver your arguments.

To Soha (2010), "speeches are a primary tool available to modern presidents to alter their current political situation and help them to govern. As such, presidents should anticipate when delivering more (or fewer) speeches is most likely to benefit them in goal achievement, whether by improving their public standing or achieving legislative policy goals. After all, presidents typically receive a bump in the polls after delivering a nationally televised address and increase their legislative success rate by speaking publicly".

While to Pudewa (2016), delivery pertains to the mechanics presenting the created speech or composition. If speaking, then memory and preparation play a large part in a speaker's confidence and mastery, and such things as vocal modulation, projection, eye contact, and gestures can be practiced and executed. It has been said that "drama is the capstone of rhetoric" for this very reason—that the final polish can make the good speech better and the better speech superb.

The delivery of President Buhari's EndSARS speech was generally poor. But his poor delivery is also influenced by his mother tongue. Not only did the body language, gesture and mien failed to "connect", but nothing indicated the President was feeling remorseful about governments failure to her youths who were demanding for better police reforms, creation of jobs and the government to fashion it's economic policy in a manner that will guarantee a country that works for all. According to Brett and McKay (2020), like the canon of style, the canon of delivery is concerned with how something is said and not just being forced to the script.

While the canon of style focuses primarily on what sort of language you use, delivery focuses on the mechanics of how you impart your message. For ancient orators, delivery meant how a speaker used his body language and hand gestures and how he changed his tone of voice during his oration.

Mastering the canon of delivery can help a speaker establish ethos with his audience. Delivery can also help an orator use pathos, or emotion, to persuade. A well placed pause or a slammed fist can elicit a desired emotion from your audience in order to make your point.

The most disappointing aspect of the speech was the fact that all through the entire delivery process, from paragraph 1 to 27, not once did the President made even a passing comment nor acknowledged what happened at Lekki Toll Gate, the citadel of the crisis.

The president, through his speech was supposed to inspire hope and calm frayed nerves. Unfortunately this was not the case.

3 Buhari's #Endsars Address and its Conformity to Rhetorical Proofs

According to Esuh (2006) "Rhetorical proofs or supports, are of classical origin, modern rhetoric only builds on them. Aristotle had theorized that the models of persuasion depending on the effects they produce in listeners are of three kinds, consisting either in the moral character of the speaker- Ethos or ethical proof; or in the production of a certain disposition in the audience - Pathos or pathetic proofs; or in the speech itself by means of real or apparent demonstration - Logos or logical proofs.

Ethos is appeal based on the character of the speaker. An ethos-driven document relies on the reputation of the author. As Esuh (2006) stated, 'Ethical proof concerns the speaker's credibility and the extent to which he is held by his audience. Aristotle stated that "good character, good sense, and concern for the welfare of the audience are the three constituents of ethical appeal". Ethos deals with the credibility of the speaker (trust).

Initial ethos (credibility held of the speaker by the audience before the speech); desired ethos- based on the speech itself and post ethos- ethos perceived after the message. The three major constituents of ethos are: sagacity or good sense, good moral character and goodwill (the three Gs).

Pathos is appeal based on emotion. Advertisements tend to be pathos-driven. According to Esuh (2006), Pathetic Proof "is the simplest way of understanding the tenets of pathos. Without the audience, there is no speech. The speech situation is a third-dimensional transaction and the audience disposition is as valid as other components- the speaker and the speech itself. It is inferred that the audience is the most important element in the speech situation and that if the speaker is to be effective, he must adjust himself and his

ideas to it. Pathetic proof is also called emotional proof. It must be designed and used to put the audience in a frame of mind to react favorably and comfortably to the purpose of the speech situation. If by any means the audience is not put in a favorable frame to be moved, the speech will lose its potency".

Logos is appeal based on logic or reason. Documents distributed by companies or corporations are logos-driven. Scholarly documents are also often logos-driven. As Esuh (2006) stated, "Logical Proof refers to the basic elements of the speech itself which the speaker employs to alter the consciousness of his audience. The two main elements of logical proofs, he notes are:

1. **Evidence** - Inartistic proof are existent proofs which are not created by the speaker, the raw materials used to establish an issue. It includes testimony of people, exhibits, witnesses, oaths, statistics, photographs/illustration, oral and video recording and other 'factual' matters capable of inducing agreement or belief.
2. **Argument** - Artistic proof is the ability of the speaker to create line of argument out of existing evidence. Evidence without creativity may lack the potency to bite.

Buhari's speech in question lacked ethos needed under the circumstance. Ethos suffered tremendously in this speech. His viewers and listeners had many reasons not to trust whatever he was saying. The speech itself was made worse by lacking the desired ethos it ought to have come with. From start to finish, either deliberately or by error, the address made no single reference to the Lekki Toll Gate crisis. An opportunity to evoke emotional appeal that connects with sensitivity and empathy was lost. This explains why outrage, frustration, disappointment grew higher after the speech than before the speech.

The speech visibly lacked Pathos. Even though the address in question was a national broadcast, his major audience was the youths who were in this instance, angry, furious, and frustrated, on rampage protesting, disrupting law and order leading to death and unimaginable destruction of public properties. A Presidential speech at this time would have centered on calming tempers, appealing for calm and most significantly, apologizing.

The mention of Farmermoni, Tradermoni, Marketmoni, N-Power, N-Tech and N-Agro in paragraphs 13 and his comment in paragraph 14 that ... "No Nigerian Government in the past has methodically and seriously approached poverty-alleviation like we have done", were perceived as mere tokenism that was meant to humiliate than empower, enslave than liberate and demobilize than

energize. Therefore, not only was logos lacking in the speech but he failed to utilize the few data and facts he had and to deliver same in a manner that advanced his course and believability. His attempt to showcase the numerous social intervention programmes of his administration as achievement of what he has done to Nigerian youths, lacked the artistic proof capable of making any emotional impact on the youths.

4 Conclusion

Speech is two-way face-to-face communication, in this case, the speech is the result of the process of thinking by a person who poured in the activities of speaking to the general public by providing a sequence of exposure in the form of a systematic in the form of a topic of information with the purpose of listeners understanding and following the communicator's intentions. Thus, rhetoric can be regarded as the ability to process various means of language in certain situations and certain purposes in the activities of communicating.

The President's speech in the aftermath of the EndSARS protest, failed the test of leadership, of being Presidential and of being sober. If there is one speech which further plummeted the President's approval rating and showed him as a leader who has lost torch and got disconnected with the reality of life, this was one as it never inspired, consoled, comforted, gave neither hope nor solace but dampened patriotism and pride in Nationhood.

Priority must therefore be made to ensure that the rhetorical canons are strictly adhered to in future presidential speeches especially in moment of crisis as almost all crisis Communication Management techniques are embedded in the rhetorical canons.

5 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is hereby recommended that: Presidential speech writers should consider the importance of adopting the five rhetoric canons- invention, dispositio, elucutio, memorial and delivery in future speech writing aid delivery of speeches that will inspire, arouse and appeal to emotions.

That efforts should be made to tutor the president on the need to improve on his elocution while making future speeches.

That future presidential speeches should consider the sensitivity of issues at stake, the mood of the nation and evoke rhetorical skills that will appeal more

to emotions and connect the President with the people rather than make him look distant and disconnected from the people or from reality as the EndSARS speech indicated.

That the power of silence or pause in delivery should be adopted in future Presidential speeches in a manner that allows body language and gestures to communicate his association with the feelings of the audience.

That efforts be intensified to prove the president's ability to use the rhetorical skill of memory in future speeches thus reducing his over dependence of the script.

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